

MAPPING OF THE RASHID 2 ROVER LANDING REGION ON THE FAR SIDE OF THE MOON : GEOLOGICAL HISTORY OF THE SOUTH POLE-AITKEN (SPA) BASIN'S NORTHERN RIM.

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Introduction: Rashid 2 is part of the Emirates Lunar Mission (ELM) program developed by the Mohammed Bin Rashid Space Centre (MBRSC) in Dubai. This rover mission, designed as a replica of the forfeit Rashid 1, will land in the northern part of the SPA basin, on the far side of the Moon, no earlier than late 2026. Rashid 2 aims to study the properties of the lunar regolith, plasma interactions at the lunar surface, and, more generally, to advance our understanding of the Moon's formation and evolution. To achieve this goal, the ~10 kg Rashid 2 rover features 3 optical cameras, including a microscopic imager, a thermal camera, four Langmuir probes and material adhesion / abrasion detection experiments [1, 2]. The present study focuses on the geological mapping of the Rashid 2 landing region, centered around the landing coordinates at 177.7° W; 23.82° S.

The SPA basin: Located in the southern hemisphere of the lunar farside, the South Pole-Aitken (SPA) basin extends from the crater Aitken to the South Pole, and is the largest and oldest impact structure on the Moon, with a diameter of about 2,500 km (Figure 1). The large basin size implies that the impact likely excavated deep lunar materials from the upper mantle or the lower crust [3,4]. Significant olivine exposures have not yet been detected within the SPA interior, but recent studies show a zoning of mafic minerals [5] with a 700 km wide high-Ca pyroxene-rich region in the SPA interior, a surrounding Mg-rich pyroxene-bearing zone, and a heterogeneous annulus on feldspathic highlands with localized pyroxene-bearing areas (mostly Mg-rich) [e.g., 6]. Moreover, the SPA interior exhibits a distinctive high-FeO chemical anomaly referred to as the SPA Compositional Anomaly (SPACA) that could reflect a pre-impact lunar crust stratified in iron [7]. Overall, the SPA basin is a complex structure recording a history of impact melting and perhaps excavation of deep crustal or upper-mantle materials of the Moon [8].

Investigating the SPA materials through the Rashid 2 mission can lead to a better understanding of the oldest and largest impact structure on the Moon, and its implications for Solar System history (e.g., the Late Heavy bombardment). To this end, the landing area in the northern rim of the SPA must be accurately mapped in order to provide the geological context for the mission.

Figure 1: The lunar farside observed with the LRO WAC. The SPA basin outline is represented by a black circle. The blue rectangle highlights the area that is mapped in this study. The yellow star indicates the centre of the Rashid 2 landing ellipse.

Data and methods: Detailed mapping of the landing region is achieved using multiple remote sensing datasets with different spatial resolutions, assembled in a Geographic Information System (GIS), as in [9]. Unit boundaries are defined from the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO) Wide Angle Camera (WAC) (100 m/pixel) and SELENE/Kaguya Terrain Camera (TC) (7.4 m/pixel) image mosaics, but also from compositional data including the Clementine band ratio mosaic, derived global maps of TiO₂ and FeO, and new global maps of lunar refractory elements calculated from the Lunar Prospector Gamma Ray Spectrometer (LP GRS) [10]. The present work is also compared to regional and global geologic maps published in 1978, 2013 and 2020 [11-13].

To obtain absolute model ages (AMAs) of the mapped units, we performed crater size-frequency distribution (CSFD) measurements. The diameters of primary craters within different units and the counting area dimensions were extracted from our GIS, and used as inputs in the Craterstats II software [14]. The AMAs were measured using the production function and the chronology functions of Neukum et al., 2001 [15]. Results are presented with a cumulative fit.

Preliminary results: The mapped region covers about $760 \text{ km} \times 810 \text{ km}$ and extends from 168°E to 165°W and from 09°S to 36°S . The study area is dominated by feldspathic material, as evidenced by red hues on the Clementine false color ratio mosaic. Evidence for volcanism is sparse within the region, but mare basalt units were identified in five craters: Aitken crater, Van de Graaf crater, Leeuwenhoek crater, Rumford crater and Lacus Oblivionis (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Kaguya orthoimages mosaic of the mapped region showing the five mare basalt units on which CSFD measurements were performed.

Basaltic deposits in Aitken yield an AMA of $3.6 (+0.05/-0.08) \text{ Ga}$, based on our CSFD measurements. Lunar maria in Van de Graaf, Leeuwenhoek, Rumford and Lacus Oblivionis were estimated at $3.7 (+0.03/-0.04) \text{ Ga}$, $3.6 (+0.06/-0.09) \text{ Ga}$, $2.3 \pm 0.1 \text{ Ga}$ and $2.6 \pm 0.2 \text{ Ga}$ respectively (Figure 3). These new ages of mare volcanism might indicate not one but two peaks in volcanic activity in the region of interest. Ongoing work focused on the mapping and dating of highlands and crater units; results will be presented at the time of the conference.

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Figure 3: Absolute model ages derived from cumulative fits with Craterstats II, to the CSFD measurements of the Aitken and Rumford basaltic deposits.

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